
Deliverable JIP1-4.6
Two additional training workshops and two webinars

Workpackage 4

Responsible Partner: 38-SVA
Contributing partners: 9-BfR, 33-NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	JIP1-4.6 Two additional training workshops and two webinars
WP and Task	WP4 – Task T-4.4
Leader	Fernanda Dórea (SVA) and Matthias Filter (BfR)
Other contributors	Estíbaliz López de Abechuco (BfR), Taras Günther (BfR), Karin Lagesen (NVI)
Due month of the deliverable	M42
Actual submission month	M42
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

ORION TRAINING AND DISSEMINATION

Executive Summary

The ORION project had planned and carried out a number of training and dissemination activities to share knowledge within the ORION consortium and with other EJP projects and partners. This also included training workshops on the use of new tools produced/adopted within the ORION project.

According to the ORION project plan, the deliverable D4.6 specifies that until M42 the ORION project has to provide "Two additional training workshops and two webinars". Due to the traveling restrictions associated with the COVID19 pandemic, trainings were conducted as online workshops.

We highlight two main trainings:

Date(s)	Training	Notes/ description
15.-19.02.2021	EJP CPD2021	In February 2021 members of the ORION project contributed to the OHEJP Continuing Professional Development (CPD) module 2021. The CPD 2021 focused on "Digital innovations for One Health professionals". Within the CPD 2021 module, the members of the ORION WP3 performed a full day training on "Data interoperability in One Health". Further, ORION partners gave presentations on the following topics: "Fast meets slow: building sustainable digital systems for bioinformatics based surveillance": WP2-NGS "The OHEJP Glossary": WP1 "Glossaryfication Web Service": WP1 In addition, ORION WP3 created an e-learning course "Linked Open Data (LOD)" within the BfR e-learning platform that remains available for CPD participants.
29.04.2020	Workshop NGS	A workshop "Practical use of NGS data webinar" led by ORION's WP2-NGS has been organized to share knowledge on best practice tools and the lessons learned on their application to OH with other OHEJP members.

And two main webinars:

Date(s)	Webinar	Notes/ description
07.06.2021	ASM2021 Satellite workshop	In the OHEJP annual scientific meeting the ORION project participated in the satellite workshop themed "Online Software Fair and Developer Meetup". Estíbaliz López de Abechuco (BfR) presented the "Glossaryfication Web Service" developed in WP1, Taras Günther (BfR) presented the "One Health Linked Data Toolbox" developed in conjunction by WP1 and WP3, Karin Lagesen presented "Practical aspects of implementing the IRIDA system as a solution for One Health bioinformatics analyses" developed by WP2-NGS.
05.10.2020	ORION EJP cogwheel workshop	A workshop summarizing the accomplishments of the ORION project, and the insights of the group into OH surveillance issues that could be continued by other OHEJP projects. A recording is available at the link provided.

With respect to the dissemination of project results, the ORION project performed during 2020-2021 a number of activities (for a complete list of ORION dissemination and publication activities see the final ORION report):

27-29.05.2020	<u>ASM 2020</u> (two oral presentations, one poster)
10.06.2020	<u>Parma Summer School</u> (oral presentation)
30.09.2020	<u>ICBO 2020</u> (oral presentation)
19.10.2020	<u>Scientific Network for ZMD (EFSA)</u> (oral presentation)
30.10.- 03.11.2020	<u>6th World One Health Congress</u> (poster presentations)
09.03.2021	<u>ORION Full consortium meeting</u> – open day
23-24.03.2021	<u>National Seminar Denmark</u> (oral presentations)
30.03.2021	<u>PAHO-WHO workshop</u> (oral presentation)
09-11.06.2021	<u>ASM 2021</u> (oral presentation and poster)
08-10.07.2021	<u>Galaxy Community Conference</u> (poster presentation)